

Budd-Chiari syndrome due to polycythemia vera with JAK2 mutation: A case report on the application of Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS).

Sanjay Kirshan Kumar *

***Correspondence to:** Sanjay Kirshan Kumar, Bahria Medical and Dental College, Karachi.

Copyright

© 2024 **Sanjay Kirshan Kumar**. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Received: 21 October 2024

Published: 25 October 2024

Introduction

We present the first reported case in Latin America of the association of Budd-Chiari Syndrome (SBC) with Polycythemia Vera (PV) in a pediatric patient who had a clinically indolent course. At the time of diagnosis, the patient had already developed complications of advanced liver disease, necessitating a portosystemic shunt as a rescue treatment. The procedure was performed successfully, with positive outcomes during follow-up.

Polycythemia Vera (PV) is a part of Philadelphia-negative myeloproliferative neoplasms, characterized by clonal erythrocytosis with normal morphology and leukocytosis. Clinical manifestations include splenomegaly, thrombosis, bleeding, and, in the long term, potential transformation to myelofibrosis or leukemia. The reported incidence varies between 0.5-4 cases per 100,000 person-years. Diagnostic criteria for PV include hematocrit >52% in men, >48% in women, or an increase in red blood cell mass >25% above predicted values, along with a mutation in the JAK2 gene (requiring both criteria). About 96% of PV patients have a JAK2 gene mutation, with 3% presenting somatic activating mutations in exons 14 (JAK2V617F) and 12 of JAK2, respectively. Calreticulin mutations (CALR: 19p13.2) are rare in PV.

Half of the patients are asymptomatic at the time of diagnosis, while others may present with various symptoms. Complications include thrombosis, hemorrhage, transformation to myelofibrosis, or leukemia, with a higher frequency in adults than in children. Management is based on risk stratification, although current risk stratifiers are not applicable to pediatric patients. Treatment involves phlebotomy to maintain hematocrit <45%, low-dose aspirin, and, for symptomatic patients, first-line use of interferon-alpha or hydroxyurea, with JAK2 inhibitors like ruxolitinib as a second-line option.

In PV, thrombosis occurs in 15% of patients, with Budd-Chiari Syndrome being the most frequent thrombotic complication in pediatric patients, predominantly affecting females. SBC is characterized by hepatic venous outflow obstruction, either in the hepatic venules, large hepatic veins, inferior vena cava, or right atrium. Primary SBC results from endoluminal obstruction (thrombosis), while secondary SBC originates from lesions outside the venous system (tumor, abscess, etc.). The most common risk factor is myeloproliferative disorders, followed by hypercoagulable states such as primary thrombophilia, protein C deficiency, factor V Leiden mutation, antiphospholipid antibody syndrome, prothrombin gene mutation, and paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria. The reported incidence and prevalence of Budd-Chiari Syndrome range from 0.168-4.09 and

2.4-33.1 per million per year, respectively.

The pathophysiology involves hepatic venous obstruction, leading to increased intrasinusoidal pressure, sinusoidal dilatation, and extravasation of erythrocytes accumulating in the Disse space. In early stages, congestion affects the perivenular zone, gradually extending to the periportal zone. Persistent hepatic hypoperfusion results in ischemic injury followed by fibrosis and nodular regenerative changes, ultimately leading to cirrhosis.

Clinical manifestations include hepatomegaly, abdominal distension, splenomegaly, ascites, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, jaundice, hepatic encephalopathy, and failure to thrive. Diagnosis relies on ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging, with Doppler ultrasound being the initial diagnostic tool for SBC. Direct imaging signs include occlusion or compression of hepatic veins or the inferior vena cava, collateral veins, and indirect signs include morphological changes in the liver with caudate lobe hypertrophy and late nodule formation. Treatment involves a stepwise therapeutic strategy, including anticoagulation, addressing the underlying cause, recanalization of occluded hepatic veins, transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS), and liver transplantation.

Prognostic indices for SBC include Child-Pugh score, Model for End-Stage Liver Disease (MELD) score (in patients over 12 years), Rotterdam BCS index, and New Clichy PI. Regular follow-up and multidisciplinary management are crucial for long-term prognosis.

Case Presentation

A 16-year-old female patient from Sinaloa, Mexico, presented with progressively worsening abdominal pain and increased abdominal girth. Initially managed with ceftriaxone for suspected gastroenteritis without response, she later developed dyspnea with minimal exertion, leading her to seek emergency care. Notably, the patient had a history of unspecified thrombophilia treated with aspirin (100 mg daily) for six years, with no hematologist follow-up in the past four years.

Physical examination revealed no signs of hepatic encephalopathy but demonstrated general pallor, bilateral basal pleural effusion, collateral venous network on the abdomen, and tense ascites. Laboratory tests were obtained upon admission (see Table 1). Doppler ultrasound of the liver indicated a heterogeneous pattern

consistent with compensated cirrhosis and vascular liver disorder resembling Budd-Chiari Syndrome.

Liver elastography showed advanced chronic liver disease. Abdominal computed tomography with venous and arterial phases confirmed caudate lobe hypertrophy compressing the inferior vena cava, right and middle suprahepatic vein thrombosis, and splenic vein dilation. The integrated diagnosis was Budd-Chiari Syndrome.

Liver biopsy revealed stage 3 fibrosis, and bone marrow biopsy showed marked megakaryocytic and granulocytic hyperplasia, left-shifted myelopoiesis, and morphological features suggestive of Polycythemia Vera. JAK2 mutation was positive, confirming the diagnosis of JAK2-positive Polycythemia Vera.

Initial management included therapeutic paracentesis, fluid restriction, subcutaneous enoxaparin (40 mg every 24 hours), spironolactone (100 mg/day), and oral propranolol (40 mg every 24 hours). As the patient's general condition improved, a transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) procedure was performed successfully, confirmed by fluoroscopy and Doppler ultrasound (see Figure 3).

The patient was discharged with overall improvement, prescribed ambulatory treatment with oral ruxolitinib (20 mg every 24 hours) and rivaroxaban (20 mg every 12 hours). A follow-up visit at six months revealed an asymptomatic patient with no pleural effusion, ascites, or edema. Laboratory parameters were within normal ranges (see Table 1).

Discussion

The patient presented with Budd-Chiari Syndrome associated with Polycythemia Vera, a rare condition in pediatric patients. The reported incidence is between 0.5-4 cases per 100,000 person-years, with myeloproliferative neoplasms being 100 times more common in adults than in children. Budd-Chiari Syndrome represents less than 0.1% of liver diseases in children in Western countries. Once the PV diagnosis is established, ongoing monitoring for thrombotic or hemorrhagic symptoms, complete blood counts, and bone marrow biopsy are essential for stratifying the patient's response to treatment (remission, disease progression, or non-response).

The patient lacked a comprehensive approach and follow-up for the prothrombotic state since childhood, a predisposing factor for developing complications of the disease. Presence of ascites, elevated bilirubin, and creatinine are associated with increased mortality risk, making invasive management a priority, factors present

in the patient at the disease onset. Imaging findings indicated advanced chronic liver disease; however, in the context of ascites, they may overestimate fibrosis degree. A liver biopsy was performed, considered the gold standard for cirrhosis diagnosis, confirming stage 3 fibrosis.

Upon Budd-Chiari Syndrome diagnosis, immediate anticoagulant therapy is recommended if there are no contraindications. The patient received low-molecular-weight heparin to achieve an anti-Xa activity of 0.5-0.8 units/mL, adhering to EASL recommendations for ascites management, including fluid restriction, therapeutic paracentesis for tense ascites, spironolactone (100 mg/day), and non-cardioselective beta-blockers like propranolol.

With improved patient conditions, a TIPS procedure was performed, a percutaneous method creating a portosystemic shunt to reduce portal resistance and immediately alleviate mesenteric venous congestion, resulting in an estimated 50% reduction in portal pressure. TIPS is the treatment of choice for Budd-Chiari Syndrome with portal hypertension unresponsive to pharmacological therapy. The patient's six-month follow-up showed asymptomatic status, normal physical examination, and laboratory parameters within normal ranges.

TIPS has achieved a 5-year transplant-free survival rate of 70% and a 5-year overall survival of 90%. Reported 5-year mortality for TIPS was 6.59%, compared to 88.8% for patients managed conservatively. Long-term follow-up with continued management is essential, considering that anticoagulation interruption or subtherapeutic anticoagulation is a primary cause of TIPS reocclusion. Additionally, monitoring PV is crucial due to the risk of progression to myelofibrosis and acute myeloid leukemia.

Liver transplantation is reserved for patients with fulminant hepatic failure, refractory ascites, and those with poor response to TIPS. Advances in surgical techniques, postoperative care, and immunosuppressive treatment have made liver transplantation an effective treatment modality, with reported survival rates of 76%, 75%, and 72% at 1, 3, and 5 years, respectively.

These diseases pose a challenge in deciding the best therapy, considering available resources and a multidisciplinary team with limited experience due to their low prevalence and high complexity. There is scarce literature on managing Budd-Chiari Syndrome in pediatric patients, with promising results reported for a stepwise treatment strategy. This strategy involves anticoagulation and addressing the underlying cause as first-line treatment, with TIPS indicated in case of treatment failure and as a therapy to alleviate portal

hypertension symptoms. Liver transplantation is reserved as a last resort due to high complication rates and limited availability of living donor organs.

Table 1. Comparative laboratory data, clinical status, and prognostic scores before and after TIPS.

Parameter	Pre-TIPS	Post-TIPS
Leukocytes	30.0 x 10 ³ /mm ³	7.96 x 10 ³ /mm ³
Hemoglobin	18.5 g/dL	11.7 g/dL
Hematocrit	58.5%	34.6%
Platelets	779,000 x 10 ³ /mm ³	402 x 10 ³ /mm ³
Neutrophils	25.1 x 10 ³ /mm ³	6.25 x 10 ³ /mm ³
Partial thromboplastin time	38.9 sec	33.5 sec
Prothrombin time	22.4 sec	13.5 sec
INR	1.71	1.1
Alanine aminotransferase	187 U/L	54 U/L
Aspartate aminotransferase	354 U/L	54 U/L
Albumin	2.8 g/dL	4.5 g/dL
Total bilirubin	2.17 mg/dL	1.40 mg/dL
Direct bilirubin	1.32 mg/dL	0.63 mg/dL
Indirect bilirubin	0.85 mg/dL	0.77 mg/dL
Serum creatinine	0.68 mg/dL	0.56 mg/dL
Hepatic encephalopathy	No	No
Diuretics	Yes	No
Child-Pugh	C	A
Clichy score >5.42	Yes	No

1 International normalized ratio

2 Clichy Score: $(\text{Ascites score} \times 0.75) + (\text{Child-Pugh score} \times 0.28) + (\text{Age} \times 0.037) + (\text{Creatinine} \times 0.0036)$
= >5.4, 5-year survival of 95%; <5.4, 5-year survival of 62%.

3 Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt

Image 1 Doppler ultrasound of liver. Right suprahepatic vein without flow on color Doppler (white arrow).

Image 2 Doppler ultrasound of liver. Middle suprahepatic vein without flow on color Doppler (white arrows).

Image 3 Doppler ultrasound of liver. Permeability of the stent in the inferior vena cava is checked (green arrows).

Image 4: Liver biopsy revealed stage 3 fibrosis

Medtronic